

Original article

CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE: ANALYSIS OF FIRST-WAVE CSRD BANKING DISCLOSURES

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Abstract: This study examines the first wave sustainability reports published by 20 European credit institutions under the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), investigating their double materiality assessment approaches and reporting practices. By employing MAXQDA software, we analysed these reports, and we have identified significant consistencies in priority sustainability matters reported, with universal coverage of climate change, workforce issues, consumer impacts, and business conduct across institutions. Our research shows that while banks effectively report on impacts, risks, and opportunities (IRO), notable challenges persist in consistently differentiating between impact and financial materiality perspectives. Financed emissions has become the main environmental concern, sometimes overshadowing other sustainability issues including water resources, pollution, and biodiversity which are interconnected. This study also identifies several comparability issues, including inconsistent value chain positioning of sustainability matters, inadequate time horizon specifications, and overreliance on indirect stakeholder consultations. Regional variations between Northern and Western and Central European institutions are observed, particularly in reporting structure and depth. The implementation of EU Taxonomy disclosures and preparation for limited assurance requirements present additional challenges for these institutions. By offering insights on CSRD implementation in the banking sector and suggesting specific ways to improve the comparability and decision-usefulness of future sustainability disclosures by credit institutions, this study adds to the literature on sustainability reporting.

Keywords: Sustainability Report, CSRD, Double Materiality Assessment, Financed Emissions, EU Taxonomy, Credit institutions

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1. Introduction

Given the current economic and social landscape, the sustainability path for undertakings seems paved with more uncertainties than opportunities. In this context, it raises questions about whether the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) has provided the anticipated value to businesses. Furthermore, following the recent introduction of the "Omnibus" package (Omnibus, 2025), which pledges significant simplification of the current regulatory landscape, it is still uncertain which are the incentives for entities that reported starting with 2025 for the financial year of 2024. The European Union has established a comprehensive regulatory framework to standardize and enhance corporate sustainability reporting across member states. This framework consists of four interconnected pillars: the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD), the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR), the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), and the EU Taxonomy Regulation. Together, these regulations form the backbone of Europe's transition toward a more sustainable and transparent financial system.

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The implementation of the directive has been stalled for several countries such as Germany, Austria, Greece, Portugal, and Malta in the EU (Appendix 1). Several other countries such as Malta, Iceland, Portugal, and Austria didn't seem to have prepared any national draft legislations by the end of 2024. Although most EU countries were at least pretending to be in the drafting phase, some others seemed to be stuck in preliminary internal discussions. In September 2024, the European Commission started infringement proceedings against 17 member states for not notifying what national measures they had adopted to transpose the CSRD into national law (European Commissions, 2024). For companies that fall under the CSRD, especially the earliest ones who need to report in 2025, this gap poses considerable risk. While the enforcement date for CSRD was January 1, 2025, for the entire EU, countries with no transposition reported voluntary.

For the banking industry, these regulations have far-reaching implications that extend beyond their own reporting obligations. Financial institutions occupy a dual role in the sustainable finance ecosystem, needing to report on their own activities while simultaneously assessing their clients' sustainability performance to meet their disclosure obligations. This creates significant data challenges, particularly in collecting comprehensive ESG data from clients, especially SMEs and non-EU entities that may not be subject to the same reporting requirements. First banks and some other financial institutions already bound by NFRD have become subject to the CSRD during 2024. They entered the applicability area of CSRD for the reporting for 2025 for the year ended 2024, which classifies these institutions as early reporters. Now, for these institutions, there is a sustainable reporting requirement that aligns with the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESSR) (EFRAG, 2023). Set to be implemented in 2025, the European Commission's "Omnibus" (Omnibus, 2025) proposal will drastically change the CSRD criteria, mandating companies to qualify by employing over 1,000 personnel, as opposed to the previous 250, alongside either surpassing €50 million in revenue or holding a €25 million balance sheet. This adds a potential 80% reduction of companies subject to the regulation, significantly shifting the dynamic for banks' value chain reporting. For accounting purposes, the CSRD as formulated presents unique challenges to banks as most reporting requirements have been drafted with non-bank corporations in mind. There was an expectation the EFRAG would publish the standards for banks by 2024 but posting deadlines have already been missed. This postponement has compelled banks to make use of other sustainability standards such as SASB.

Based on the current evolutions related to the legislation in place, our study proposes a comprehensive analysis of the first wave of sustainability reports published by European credit institutions. In this context, we propose the following research objectives: firstly, there is a need for understanding what the overall approach of the first wave reporting credit institutions is by identifying the most relevant reporting areas (ESG); secondly, what are the main similarities and differences between reporting credit institutions and thirdly, what are the main areas for improvement. In order to respond to these research goals, we have analysed 20 sustainability reports published by first wave reporting entities, focused on credit institutions. The focus on these entities comes from the fact that the CSRD regulation did not consider specific complexities related to the reporting of these entities. As known, the most impactful effects of the banks come from their value chain does not form own operations and in the context of a constrained data availability, we consider that analysing how banks reported under CSRD can provide valuable insights for future improvements in the regulatory framework. Our findings reveal that while banks consistently prioritize climate change (E1), own workforce (S1), consumer and end-users (S4), and governance (G1), they demonstrate significant inconsistencies in applying the double materiality principle, particularly in differentiating between impacts and financial materiality. The research contributes to sustainability reporting literature by identifying key challenges in CSRD implementation for financial institutions and proposing concrete recommendations for enhancing the comparability and decision-usefulness of sustainability disclosures in the banking sector.

This study is

2. Legislative context

2.1. Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD)

In 2014, the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD) (Directive 2014/95/EU, 2019) was introduced, coming into effect by the year 2018. This marked the EU's first major calculation considering mandatory sustainability reports. The directive required the disclosure of information related to environmental and social issues, employees, human rights, and anticorruption/ bribery on public interest limited companies with more than 500 employees. It covered roughly 11,000 public interest limited companies such as listed companies, banks, and insurance companies based in EU member countries. The NFRD opted for a "comply or explain" strategy which gave leeway to companies in regard to omitting policies in some areas if there are valid justifications. As under other areas of freedom of business, companies are free to include the management report at the end of the accounts or

submit a distinct document. The latter, however, must include the five areas of required disclosures: environmental protection, social responsibility and treatment of employees, respect of human rights, measures to prevent corruption and promote formation of voluntary supervision by a diversified council. The European Commission published non-binding guidelines in 2017, later updating them in 2019 with further guidance on climate-related information. Even with its revolutionary attributes, the NFRD had serious shortcomings in practice. An absence of specific and coherent reporting frameworks resulted in several disclosures being null or incomplete at both the corporate and industry levels. There were no verification requirements leading to unreliable claims which made it impossible for investors and other users of the data to sustain comparisons with peers in sustainability reporting. These gaps within the NFRD ultimately led to the formulation of more sophisticated regulations to fill these voids.

2.2. Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)

Complementary to NFRD legislation, the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2019/2088, 2019) enforced its provisions in March 2021, focusing on financial market participants and their advisers. SFDR imposes transparency requirements on investment firms, asset managers, insurance companies, pension funds, and financial advisers on dealing with the concerns of sustainability. On the micro level, financial market participants are expected to have policies relating to the integration of sustainability risks communicated to the public in decision-making processes concerning investments (Article 3). They shall also provide assertions concerning their due diligence policies in relation to the principal adverse impacts of investment decisions on sustainability factors or disaffirm why such impacts are ignored (Article 4). Also, there is a need to explain how the policies on remuneration are aligned with the integration of sustainability risks (Article 5).

The most notable change brought by the SFDR is in its product-level classification scheme. Financial products are divided into three categories: Article 6 products which do not integrate any sustainability aspect, Article 8 products that ‘light green’ and foster environmental or social characteristics (often called “light green”), and Article 9 products that have sustainable investment as their core objective (also known as “dark green”). This classification has fundamentally changed the European investment landscape because asset managers have had to redesign their product suites to comply with Articles 8 and 9. The regulation requires disclosure on the company website, in pre-contractual documents, and in periodic reporting. The Regulation is accompanied by detailed Regulatory Technical Standards (RTS) which outline mandatory indicators for adverse impact and offer ready templates for standardized disclosure. The SFDR is built on a double materiality approach considering both the impact sustainability concerns pose to the financial product, and the investment’s impact on sustainability factors. It is also linked with the EU Taxonomy (Regulation (EU) 2020/852, 2020), demanding that Article 8 and 9 products disclose how they meet the requirements of the Taxonomy.

2.3. Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)

Three years back adopting The Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772, 2023) marked a complete revision of the European Union’s sustainability reporting system. The CSRD reporting framework expands both coverage and requirements relative to the NFRD, mandating reporting by all large EU firms that satisfy at least two out of these three conditions: total balance sheet of €40 million, revenue of €80 million, or over 250 employees. It additionally applies to all regulated market EU listed companies (excluding micro enterprises), listed SMEs (subsidized standards with an opt-out until 2028), as well as non-EU firms with a significant presence in the EU (more than €150 million revenue generated in the EU and having at least one subsidiary or branch in the EU). This expansion incorporates approximately 50,000 firms to the sustainability reporting requirements, a massive increase from 11,000 that were covered by the NFRD. The CSRD’s foundation rests on establishing the obligatory European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) (EFRAG, 2023), formed by EFRAG and adopted by the Commission. These standards include overarching requirements of general principles, strategy, governance, and the processes for materiality assessment along with topical standards for specific environmental, social, and governance disclosures, with other supplementary standards for specific sectors being developed on a continuous basis. The CSRD mandates companies to evaluate impact materiality and financial materiality, meaning that self-reporting CSR grading companies must consider their sustainability impact on people and the environment alongside how business value is influenced by sustainability factors. This latter type of approach is more integrated because it serves the sustainability concern of a wider range of stakeholders. In order to improve accessibility and facilitate easier comparisons, sustainability information should be coded in machine-readable formats which aid in the development of the European Single Access Point (ESAP), the unified repository for company data. The directive makes additional changes to incorporate assurance requirements, with initial stipulations as limited assurance on sustainability information and potential future increased to reasonable assurance. Unlike the

NFRD, which gave flexibility for standalone reporting, the CSRD makes it mandatory for sustainability information to be integrated into the management report, thus blurring the boundary, or making more holistic, between financial and non-financial information. Companies are expected to provide forward-looking statements detailing their objectives and plans, including capital expenditure alignment towards the Paris Agreement, detailing spending that supports the agreement. The scope of reporting goes beyond direct control of the firm to relevant value chain related information.

The implementation of the CSRD started in 2025 for the companies already covered by NFRD. Other large firms previously not covered by NFRD will report starting from 2026 (starting from year 2025). At this time, considering the “Omnibus” package⁴, the applicability area has been amended.

2.4. EU Taxonomy Regulation

The EU Taxonomy Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2019/2088, 2019) came into effect in January 2022, establishing a classification system that allocates varying degrees of environmental sustainability to economic activities. This regulation aims at creating a common understanding for investors, businesses, and public administrators on which economic activities can be deemed environmentally safe and putting to rest any misleading claims aimed at garnering environmental sympathy (greenwashing). This regulation also helps in directing the market towards the investments that are essential for attaining carbon neutrality. The above-mentioned legislation is based on six mentioned climatic matters. Taxonomy is aligned with a voluntary action framework which states an economic activity must contribute to one of the above-mentioned objectives without inflicting significant harm while adhering to the others. Furthermore, it also has to meet the so-called social impact criteria which are based on international standards such as the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights. The regulation has defined disclosure obligations for each category of company. Non-financial firms are required to disclose the proportion of their turnover, capital expenditures (CapEx), and operational expenditures (OpEx) of Taxonomy-aligned activities. Other financial entities such as banks and asset managers need to disclose their Green Asset Ratio (GAR) as well as other key performance indicators tracking the alignment of their financing activities with the Taxonomy.

The European Commission implements technical screening criteria through a variety of delegated acts, including the Climate Delegated Act (which includes climate mitigation and adaptation criteria) (Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2486, 2023), the Complementary Delegated Act (which focuses on nuclear and natural gas activities) (Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/1214, 2022), and the Article 8 Delegated Act (which outlines disclosure methodology) (Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2178, 2021). These criteria are updated regularly with the assistance of the Platform on Sustainable Finance.

3. Methods

Most of the entities that entered wave 1 of reporting under CSRD are credit institutions. The reporting landscape for a manufacturing versus financial institutions implies different judgements that need to be performed starting with the double materiality assessment, disclosures to be reported and EU taxonomy. Our study is based on reviewing a number of 20 sustainability reports of the first publishing credit institutions from EU countries for the year ended 2024 (Appendix 1).

We have retrieved the sustainability reports which are an integral part of the Annual Report from each entity's website. Firstly, we have analyzed each banks' double materiality assessment process and its outcome, then we have analysed key indicators and methodologies used in order to establish if comparability of information between peers was achieved namely: Scope 3 Category 15 greenhouse emissions, EU Taxonomy key performance indicators and gender pay-gap. Contrarily to Operato et al. (2025), we consider that comparability can be achieved only by applying uniform structure of the reports between entities. It is not a matter of units in which are presented but of methodologies employed to arrive at the outcome.

We have employed MAXQDA software in order to analyse the reports. Respectively, we have coded each segment of interest from the Sustainability Reports and then; after coding each aspect (Appendix 2), we analysed the results obtained by the length of the chapter, type of disclosed information, distance matrix between two relevant groups identified, namely northern European countries and western and central European countries. Group one (Northern Countries) contain 8 reports sample while western and central countries contain 12 analysed reports.

⁴ For more details, please refer to Omnibus (2025) at https://commission.europa.eu/publications/omnibus-i_en

4. Results and discussions

4.1. General content

Table 1 presents the summary statistics related to chapter lengths across the 20 CSRD sustainability reports analyzed. As it can be observed, there are revealed clear patterns in how banks allocate space to different ESG components. Environmental reporting dominates these first-wave reports, accounting for nearly half (49.1%) of total report length with an average of 69.9 pages. This substantial emphasis reflects both the maturity of environmental reporting frameworks and the detailed requirements of the EU Taxonomy regulation. The significant gap between average (69.9 pages) and median (55.5 pages) environmental section lengths indicates some reports contain exceptionally comprehensive environmental disclosures that skew the overall average upward.

Table 1: Summary statistics

Metric	ESRS 2	Environmental (E1-E5) and EU Taxonomy	Social (S1-S4)	Governance (G1)
Average	34.00	69.90	28.11	10.37
Median	26.50	55.50	28.00	9.00
Min	6.00	15.00	4.00	2.00
Max	94.00	181.00	61.00	49.00

Source: Authors' work

Note: The length of the Environmental section (E1-E5) also includes the disclosures related to EU Taxonomy including Templates from the Delegated Act, Annex V and Annex XII.

The difference between minimum and maximum disclosed information related to environmental aspects is related to disclosure requirements E1-1, namely transition plan for climate change mitigation. Only half of the banks in our sample have developed formal climate transition plans, while the remaining 50% have yet to establish these critical roadmaps for managing climate risks and opportunities. Similarly, climate resilience analysis has been adopted by precisely half of the institutions surveyed, indicating that comprehensive climate stress testing remains an emerging practice rather than an established standard. We also noted that executive compensation linked to sustainability objectives has gained more traction, with 65% of banks implementing incentive schemes that align leadership rewards with environmental performance. Worth mentioning is that 35% of the banks have remuneration policies related to ESG-related KPIs but not to greenhouse emissions reduction targets (quantitative).

Figure 1: Range of Chapter Lengths

Source: Authors' work

General disclosures under ESRS 2 constitute the second most substantial portion of reports (Figure 2), representing 23.9% of content with an average of 34 pages. This section shows considerable variation across

companies, with page counts ranging from a minimum of just 6 pages to a maximum of 94 pages (Figure 1). The disparity between average (34 pages) and median (26.5 pages) values suggests that while most companies provide moderate-length general disclosures, some organizations produce exceptionally detailed ESRS 2 sections, perhaps reflecting different interpretations of requirements or varying availability of material information. Social disclosures (S1-S4) represent 19.7% of total report content, averaging 28.1 pages. Notably, social reporting demonstrates the most consistent approach across companies, with nearly identical average (28.1) and median (28.0) values. This consistency suggests more uniform interpretation of social reporting requirements among this first wave of reporting companies, though the range from 4 to 61 pages still indicates significant differences in approach or level of detail provided by some organizations. We note that Nordic countries such as Denmark and Finland tend to disclose information in a more compact way than other countries. We have observed that policies take up to 85% of the total social disclosures with only 25% covering quantitative data and methodology explanation for the indicators presented.

Figure 2: Proportion of total length of the report

Source: Authors' work

Governance disclosures (G1) receive the least attention in these reports, constituting just 7.3% of total content with an average of only 10.4 pages. This relatively limited coverage may reflect either more streamlined governance reporting requirements or potentially represent an opportunity for more comprehensive governance disclosures in future reporting cycles. The range of governance reporting (2 to 49 pages) indicates some companies are taking a much more detailed approach than others in this area.

4.2. Disclosures structure

In order to identify the most relevant information disclosed, we have created a code system to flag the representative quantitative and/or qualitative data. We have coded a total of 1,823 segments for the sustainability reports analyzed (Table 2).

Table 2: Coded segments

Group	Name	Coded Segments
Northern Countries	Jyske Bank	143
Northern Countries	Saxo Bank	65
Northern Countries	Sydbank	53
Northern Countries	Danske Bank	93
Northern Countries	Nordea	89
Northern Countries	Nykredit	46
Northern Countries	Ringkjøbing Landbobank	57

Northern Countries	Spar Nord Bank	97
Western and Central Countries	Addiko Bank	116
Western and Central Countries	Erste Group Bank	92
Western and Central Countries	Raiffeisen Bank International	91
Western and Central Countries	BNP Paribas	79
Western and Central Countries	Credit Mutel Arkea	182
Western and Central Countries	HSBC Continental Europe	108
Western and Central Countries	Societe Generale France	57
Western and Central Countries	Unicredit Group	113
Western and Central Countries	Banca Transilvania	83
Western and Central Countries	BRD Romania	86
Western and Central Countries	Tatra Bank	116
Western and Central Countries	Raiffeisen Bank Romania	130

Source: Authors' work

We observe that Western and Central European banks have far more developed disclosure practices than Northern European banks (Figure 3), with Western and Central European banks averaging 104.4 coded segments per report compared to 80.4 for Northern European banks, representing a 30% discrepancy in reporting volume. This gap is even wider for medians (100 vs 77 segments) indicating greater reporting practices systematized at a particular region, as opposed to random chance or outlier influence.

With regard to coded segments, we observed some variability within the data, with a minimum of 46 (Nykredit) to a maximum of 182 (Credit Mutel Arkea). Such wide variation suggests that these reporting boundaries, or operating models, are at different levels of maturity, as far as implementation is concerned. The lower segments are predominantly occupied by Northern banks, with half of these institutions reporting fewer than 70 segments, while Western and Central banks concentrate in the medium-to-high ranges (70-129 segments), which indicates more consistent and comprehensive disclosure practices among the latter group. We note that the lower segments do not denote less comprehensive disclosures, but more compact ones. The geographical allocation illustrate the differences in reporting practices. Western and Central European banks appeared to have a stronger pattern as 75% of them were in the medium to high range, meaning that there is a greater propensity among them to report on sustainability issues. In contrast, Northern banks show a bimodal distribution with some institutions reporting very low segment counts and others reporting relatively high segment counts. They seem to have more diverse reported disclosures, which gives the data a more scattered appearance.

Figure 3: Distribution of coded segments

Source: Authors' work

4.3. Content of reports

As specified by ESRS 1, the companies should start their double materiality assessment process (DMA) by firstly understanding their value chain and current context of the company. Related to the definition of value chain, all banks in our sample, some more comprehensively than others, have considered their core banking services (loans, payment services, and funding), investment services: Asset management and investment products insurance offerings (both life and non-life insurance products) and other specialised services (private equity). For all financial institutions included in our sample, we note that the most complex to define value chain is the downstream. We observed that the downstream value chain is usually approached by applying multi-tiered customer segmentation strategy. The entities primarily organized their customers into distinct categories based on size and organizational structure:

1. Individual/Retail Customers: Personal banking clients
2. Business Clients: Further subdivided into SMEs and larger corporate clients
3. Institutional Clients: Including investors, sovereigns, and other financial institutions

Through code comparison analysis, we found that the predominant forms of interacting with the stakeholders are mainly through indirect consultations (Table 3). Such an approach based on indirect methods attention through surveys, reports, and speeches pose numerous significant challenges: it fosters an arms-length relationship that may ignore subtle grievances, creates information imposing asymmetry where banks administer control over the engagement format, restricts free conversation that could highlight notable revelations, and is likely to bias more positive responses when channeled through official structures. Moreover, indirect approaches of engagement will serve to meet the minimum regulatory standards without portraying the true depth of stakeholder sentiment required for sustainable changes and efficient risk management.

Table 3: Methods of engagement with stakeholders

Stakeholder Category	Engagement Methods
Customers	Satisfaction surveys, Customer panels, Customer events
Employees	Employee surveys, Diversity committees, Health and safety initiatives, Performance dialogues, Employee representatives
Investors	Presentations, Conference calls, One-on-one meetings, Financial reporting
Regulators	Regular meetings, Inspections, Thematic studies
Suppliers	Regular meetings, Tendering processes, Performance reviews, Workshops
Industry & Community	Committee participation, Social initiatives, NGOs dialogues, Volunteering in local communities
Institutional Partners	Meetings with investing platforms, Regular communications, Forums
Governance	Board of Directors meetings, Regular communication
Media & Rating Agencies	Press interactions, Rating processes, Information sharing
Policymakers	Engagement on financial regulations, Policy discussions

Source: Authors' work

Note: This table presents a summary based on coded segments for a sample of 20 sustainability reports of credit institutions.

Regarding impacts, risk and opportunities we observed a tendency either to identify mostly negative impacts and risk or positive impact (opportunities were rarely identified probably due to lack of quantitative data). We have analyzed the codes “Material sustainability ammeters” and “IRO” and we observed that all entities prioritized climate change mitigation, with most also addressing adaptation (80%) and energy use (75%). Banks consistently reported on financed emissions, acknowledging their role in greenhouse gas emissions through lending and investment activities. Also, all banks report on working conditions (100%), with near-universal coverage of equal treatment matters (95%). We note that only one bank considered gender pay-gap and total remuneration indicators as not material.

Related to S4, consumer-related issues were comprehensively covered, particularly privacy (90%), information access (85%), and inclusion (90%). Banks consistently recognize data privacy as both an ethical obligation and a significant risk area. Governance matters are extensively addressed, with corporate culture (90%), whistleblower protection (90%), and anti-corruption (95%) receiving substantial attention. Money laundering prevention which was identified as an entity-specific topics by 60% of the banks in our sample was considered significant and relevant disclosures were presented.

Figure 4: ESRS sustainability matters coverage

Source: Authors' work

Note: E1 denotes Climate change, E2 denotes Pollution, E3 denotes Water and Marine resources, E4 denotes Biodiversity, E5 denotes Circular Economy, S1 denotes Own workforce, S2 denotes Workers in the value chain, S3 denotes Affected communities, S4 denotes Consumers and end-users and G1 denotes Governances as defined in ESRS (ESRS, 2023) with all sub-topic and sub-sub-topics included under each sustainability matter.

By analysing IROs, we observed that risks received universal coverage as banks integrate sustainability considerations into their established risk management frameworks, while negative impacts and opportunities are reported at nearly identical rates (95%) (Figure 5), reflecting a balanced implementation of the double materiality principle. Financial institutions demonstrate a balanced approach to risk identification, categorizing sustainability challenges into transition, physical, and reputational risks, while their impact reporting focuses heavily on financed emissions and downstream effects rather than upstream supply chain impacts. Positive impacts (90%) tend to be communicated through qualitative narratives rather than quantitative metrics, emphasizing sustainable finance products, employee development, and financial inclusion. We note that some entities have identified mostly only positive impacts on social aspects which could denote a misunderstanding between a positive impact and the effect of the policies implemented.

Figure 5: Impacts, risks and opportunities

Source: Authors' work

Generally, all credit institutions undertook the Double Materiality Assessment process in the same manner. The relative equal focus on these IRO components indicates that the CSRD has successfully achieved comprehensive reporting disclosure among banks, albeit with significant focus on climate issues compared to other environmental or social factors, suggesting differences in methodological development across the sustainability domains. The dataset includes banks from the Northern regions (40 %) and Western/Central Europe (60 %), showing marginal differences in the regional aspects of sustainability reporting while maintaining parallels in its fundamental components. Northern European banks tend to use a more abridged and systematic way in presenting their impacts, risks, and opportunities. They prefer to be as clear and straightforward as possible (Figure 5). On the contrary,

Western/Central European institutions appear to offer thorough descriptions of the implementation of certain sustainable development strategies as part of richer contextual frameworks. Nordic banks show a peculiar working conditions for employees focus, characteristic of the region’s robust workplace rights and social welfare tradition. At the same time, Western European banks seem to provide much more detailed examination of climate change adaptation practices, which could point to greater vulnerability to or concern about physical climate risk in those regions. These differences demonstrate the interaction of regional regulatory systems with cultural context and business landscape which affect the approach to reporting within the uniform standards of CSRD.

Figure 5: Regional comparison

Source: Authors’ work

Our analysis of 20 European banks' CSRD reports reveals both strengths and opportunities for improvement in sustainability reporting practices (Figure 7). Banks demonstrate strong alignment on core sustainability matters, with universal coverage of climate change, workforce issues, consumer impacts, and business conduct. The widespread adoption of double materiality principles is evident, with nearly all banks reporting both impacts (95%) and risks/opportunities (95-100%). However, significant gaps persist in coverage of certain sustainability matters, particularly pollution, water resources, and workers in the value chain probably due to lack of value chain data availability.

Moreover, the code-based similarity matrix (Figure 7) reveals clear patterns in how European banks handle their CSRD sustainability reporting, indicating both standardization trends and significant differences in implementation strategies. The main pattern suggests strong alignment in which sustainability issues these institutions address and probably reflects adherence to core CSRD criteria since it shows a large homogeneous group of banks—including both Northern and Western/Central institutions—with identical code usage patterns as shown by 0.00 distances.

In contrast, a small cluster of Northern European banks (namely Jyske Bank, Saxo Bank, and Sydbank) show very similar but distinct patterns among themselves (with minimal distances of 0.01- 0.12), indicating they have adopted a slightly different approach to sustainability reporting while maintaining consistency within their group. Most notably, Credit Mutel Arkea emerges as a significant outlier with dramatically different code implementation (with distances ranging from 4.66 to 14.48 from all other institutions), which aligns with our previous finding that this bank reported more positive impacts, suggesting it addresses sustainability dimensions beyond what other institutions cover. Banca Transilvania, on the other hand, may reflect a hybrid reporting strategy drawing from several reporting approaches since it includes components from both the main group and the Northern cluster (distances varying from 0.12 to 0.73 with the first cluster and 0.63 with the main group). Clustering patterns cross regional borders, with both Northern and Western/Central credit institutions frequently exhibiting same implementation strategies, which implies that methodological elements and reporting frameworks have more impact on sustainability disclosure practices than geographic or regional elements. This study shows that although CSRD has effectively created basic reporting components that seem universal across European banks, there are different ways certain codes or subjects’ institutions decide to include, with some possibly going beyond minimum standards to cover more sustainability aspects.

Figure 7: Code-based similarity matrix

Document name	Jyske Bank	Saxo Bank	Sydbank	BNP Paribas	Credit Mutel Arkea	Danske Bank	HSBC Continental Europe	Nordea	Nykredit	Ringkjøbing Landbobank	Societe Generale France	Spar Nord Bank	Unicredit Group	Banca Transilvania	BRD Romania	Raiffeisen Bank Romania	Tatra Bank
Northern Countries > Jyske Bank	0.00	0.01	0.12	0.03	5.43	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18	2.18	0.47	2.18	2.18	2.18
Northern Countries > Saxo Bank	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.08	5.94	1.87	1.87	1.87	1.87	1.87	1.87	1.87	1.87	0.33	1.87	1.87	1.87
Northern Countries > Sydbank	0.12	0.06	0.00	0.26	7.14	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28	0.12	1.28	1.28	1.28
Western and Central Countries > BNP Paribas	0.03	0.08	0.26	0.00	4.66	2.71	2.71	2.71	2.71	2.71	2.71	2.71	2.71	0.73	2.71	2.71	2.71
Western and Central Countries > Credit Mutel Arkea	5.43	5.94	7.14	4.66	0.00	14.48	14.48	14.48	14.48	14.48	14.48	14.48	14.48	9.08	14.48	14.48	14.48
Northern Countries > Danske Bank	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Western and Central Countries > HSBC Continental Europe	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Northern Countries > Nordea	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Northern Countries > Nykredit	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Northern Countries > Ringkjøbing Landbobank	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Western and Central Countries > Societe Generale France	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Northern Countries > Spar Nord Bank	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Western and Central Countries > Unicredit Group	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Western and Central Countries > Banca Transilvania	0.47	0.33	0.12	0.73	9.08	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.00	0.63	0.63	0.63
Western and Central Countries > BRD Romania	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Western and Central Countries > Raiffeisen Bank Romania	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
Western and Central Countries > Tatra Bank	2.18	1.87	1.28	2.71	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00

Source: Authors' work

5. Conclusion

The shift outlined in the EU's integrated system of sustainability reporting marks its change in corporate disclosure from ad-hoc and voluntary reporting to compulsory and uniform addressing the integration of both financial and non-financial data. This shift is intended to redirect investment capital to sustainably supported corporations, increase corporate responsiveness, and aid to climate and environmental objectives of the EU as set forth in the European Green Deal. For the banking industry, there is concern complexity of cross-sectoral regulation may create a restrictive environment posing financial institutions as the dominant participants in the transition towards sustainability.

The large ranges observed during our analysis for all ESG areas indicates the multitude of challenges entities face when reporting for the first time under the CSRD framework. Reporting first-time compliance with set minimum and maximum values differing by multiples greater than fifteen in some instances suggests companies are utilizing a wide-range approach to meet the CSRD. This variation stems from differing levels of maturity in reporting, sector-specific components, and distinct materiality frameworks. Differing methodologies employed by organizations will likely change as the practice of CSRD reporting evolves and more standardized structures and lengths of reports emerge.

Businesses strategizing for CSRD compliance should use these insights while resource planning and designing the reporting structure. The results illustrate that environmental disclosures will consume the most time and resource investments, followed by overarching disclosures, social issues, and governance reporting. The significant variances noticed also suggest that companies have great discretion on how detailed their reports should be relative to their circumstances. This flexibility is conditioned on their materiality frameworks, along with the specifics of their business activities.

The purpose of this paper was to understand of the CSRD framework is delivering what it has promised, a standardized reporting framework which enhances comparability and understandability. We chose not to make a comparison between quantitative indicators because some of them, such as financed emissions are calculated differently (for example, countries from Northern Europe apply a different methodology which specific assets classes than the rest of the countries) or green asset ratio (GAR) which is highly impacted by the business segments of a bank (if a credit institution has more exposure to SMEs, the main KPI will be highly affected but this does not mean that the activities financed are not eligible or even aligned).

Investigating the sample showed multiple connections which may significantly obstruct the efficiency of sustainability disclosures. Banks often fail to distinct between risks and negative impacts or opportunities and positive impacts. This shows a lack of comprehension regarding the double materiality principle and its application. The level classification of sustainability topics is extremely difficult to distinguish because the gaps between primary topics, sub-topics, and sub-sub-topics are clearly presented by all entities, making it easier to not differentiate between institutions when trying to cross check disclosures. Moreover, the placement within the value chain of impacts, risks, and opportunities (IROs) sustain gaps with the ability to comprehend where sustainability issues arise across bank operations and relations.

Another problematic area is time horizon setting since banks either do not provide specifications at all or rationalize applying the same time horizons onto impact and financial materiality without justification (given the differences which exist due to the maturity of their assets and liabilities which affect financial materiality). We noted that some banks inappropriately treat particular datapoints as immaterial which do not account for critical stakeholder groups and are arguably information rich from the perspective of decision making. Another important issue is the overreliance on indirect stakeholder engagement as opposed to direct interaction which lowers the quality of materiality assessments and has profound negative impacts on relevance. far too many reports describe the policies and processes within the organization, as opposed to the actual data reflecting performance which leads to unreported sustainability performance, thus creating an imbalance.

Therefore, based on our analysis, we recommend for enhancement of CSRD reporting quality and comparability the following: credit institutions should establish clear distinctions between impacts and financial materiality using standardized terminology and criteria, avoiding identical descriptions for risks/negative impacts or opportunities/positive impacts. Reports should adopt consistent hierarchical structures that clearly identify topic levels and explicitly map each IRO's position in the value chain. Time horizon methodologies should differentiate between impact and financial materiality trajectories with appropriate justifications, while materiality assessments should incorporate broader stakeholder relevance criteria. Banks should supplement their current indirect stakeholder consultations with more robust direct engagement processes, particularly with key stakeholder groups, and ensure a balanced approach between policy descriptions and performance metrics, emphasizing outcome-based disclosure rather than extensive policy presentations.

Declarations (if necessary)

At the end of the manuscript, include the following sections:

- **Competing interests' declaration:** No potential conflicts of interest identified.
- **Data availability statement:** Data supporting the study can be accessed at request from the authors.

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Appendix:

Appendix 1: Transposition and implementation status in EU

Country	Transposition Status	Status
Austria	Not transposed	One of the countries that has not launched consultation or introduced legislation as of late 2024
Belgium	Legislation proposed	Introduced implementing legislation in late 2024
Bulgaria	Status unclear	Limited information available in recent trackers
Croatia	Fully transposed	Adopted legislation transposing the CSRD in July 2024
Cyprus	Legislation proposed	Introduced proposed legislation in July 2024
Czech Republic	Fully transposed	In time transposition of the directive
Denmark	Fully transposed	In time transposition of the directive
Estonia	Fully transposed	Approved implementing legislation by the end of 2024
Finland	Fully transposed	Completed transposition
France	Fully transposed	Notable exception among founding EU members for transposing on time
Germany	Legislation proposed	Introduced proposed legislation in July 2024, but facing political deadlock
Greece	Fully transposed	Approved implementing legislation by the end of 2024
Hungary	Fully transposed	Completed transposition
Ireland	Fully transposed	Transposed the directive on time
Italy	Legislation proposed	Introduced proposed legislation mid-2024
Latvia	Fully transposed	Adopted legislation transposing the CSRD in September 2024
Lithuania	Fully transposed	Completed transposition
Luxembourg	Status unclear	Limited information available in recent trackers
Malta	Not transposed	One of the countries that has not launched consultation or introduced legislation
Netherlands	Legislation proposed	Introduced proposed legislation mid-2024
Poland	Legislation proposed	Introduced implementing legislation in late 2024
Portugal	Not transposed	One of the countries that has not launched consultation or introduced legislation
Romania	Fully transposed	In time transposition of the directive
Slovakia	Fully transposed	In time transposition of the directive
Slovenia	Status unclear	Limited information available in recent trackers
Spain	Held consultation	Progress beyond consultation stage unclear
Sweden	Fully transposed	In time transposition of the directive

Source: Authors' work based on information retrieved from: European Parliament and Council of the European Union, (2024).

Appendix 2: Overview of codes

Parent code	Code	Coded segments	Meaning of coded segment
No of members Board of Directors (BoD)	% male BoD	8	This code marks the percentage of men in Board of Directors.
No of senior management	% male executive	9	This code marks the percentage of men in management positions.
Governance over Sustainability Reporting	No of senior management	9	This code denotes the total number of members in the management positions.
Governance over Sustainability Reporting	No of members BoD	11	This code denotes the total number of members in the Board of Directors.
ESRS E - Environment	Transition plan	11	This code flags the reports parts related to Transition plan as defined in the disclosure requirement E1-1 ESRS.
No of senior management	% female executive	12	This code marks the percentage of women in management positions.
No of members Board of Directors (BoD)	% female BoD	12	This code marks the percentage of women in Board of Directors.
Summary of disclosures	Phased-in disclosures	13	This code marks the phased-in disclosures.
ESRS 2 - General Requirements	Incentive scheme	13	This code was used to flag if the entity has in place an incentive scheme DR GOV-3
ESRS 2 - General Requirements	Value chain	15	This code denotes the narrative disclosures related to the identification of the value chain actors.
ESRS E - Environment	Resilience analysis	15	This code represents and flags the resilience analysis undertaken by the entity (resilience analysis as defined by ESRS).
ESRS 2 - General Requirements	Stakeholders' engagement	15	This code denotes the narrative disclosures related to consultations with stakeholders.
Scope 3 Category 15	Framework Financed emissions	16	This code denotes the framework used for the estimation of GHG emissions, Scope 3, Category 15 "Investments" as defined in the GHG Protocol.
Total GHG emissions	Emissions intensity	16	This code flags the value disclosed for financed emissions intensity by the entity.
ESRS 2 - General Requirements	Time horizons	17	This code is related to how each entity has defined its time horizons for the double materiality assessment purpose.
ESRS E - Environment	Sustainable financing	17	This code flags the narrative and numerical information presented by the undertakings related to sustainable finance exposures.
ESRS S- Social	Total remuneration ratio	18	This code flags the numerical value of the total remuneration ratio.
Total GHG emissions	Scope 2 location-based	19	This code denotes the total GHG emissions Scope 2 calculated by location-based approach as defined in GHG Protocol.

ESRS S- Social	Unadjusted gender pay gap	19	This code flags the numerical value of the unadjusted gender pay-gap.
Total GHG emissions	Scope 2 market-based	19	This code denotes the total GHG emissions Scope 2 calculated by market-based approach as defined in GHG Protocol.
EU Taxonomy	GAR KPI Stock Turnover based	19	This code flags the numerical value as percentage of the main KPI (GAR stock) based on turnover as defined in the Delegated Act (EU Directive 2021/2178).
EU Taxonomy	% Covered assets	19	This code flags the numerical value as percentage of the covered assets as defined in the Delegated Act (EU Directive 2021/2178).
EU Taxonomy	GAR KPI Stock Capex based	19	This code flags the numerical value as percentage of the main KPI (GAR stock) based on CapEx as defined in the Delegated Act (EU Directive 2021/2178).
Total GHG emissions	Scope 1	19	This code denotes the total GHG emissions Scope 1 as defined in GHG Protocol.
EU Taxonomy	% assets excluded from GAR calculation	19	This code flags the numerical value as percentage of the assets excluded from GAR calculation as defined in the Delegated Act (EU Directive 2021/2178).
ESRS E - Environment	Total GHG emissions	20	This code denotes the value of Total GHG emissions (location-based).
ESRS 2 - General Requirements	Summary of disclosures	24	This code denotes the summary (reference table) with the disclosure requirements presented/not presented by the entity.
Scope 3 all categories	Scope 3 Category 15	24	This code denotes the total GHG emissions Scope 3 Category 15 "Investments" as defined in GHG Protocol.
ESRS E - Environment	EU Taxonomy	24	This code flags the qualitative disclosures related to the EU Taxonomy.
Transition plan	Targets related to environment impacts	25	This code flags the quantitative targets related to environment impacts.
Value chain	Own operations	28	This code flags the own operations identified by the entity.
Total GHG emissions	Scope 3 all categories	29	This code denotes the total GHG emissions Scope 3 (all 15 categories) as defined in the GHG Protocol.
ESRS 2 - General Requirements	Governance over Sustainability Reporting	30	This code was used to flag the segments from the Sustainability Report related to the governance over CSRD reporting process.
Value chain	Upstream	31	This code flags the upstream value chain identified by the entity.
Value chain	Downstream	38	This code flags the downstream value chain identified by the entity
Stakeholders' engagement	Category stakeholder	141	This code represents the category of stakeholder identified by the undertaking.
Category stakeholder	Method of engagement	160	This code flags the method of engagement / consultation with the stakeholders identified as relevant by the undertaking.
ESRS 2 - General Requirements	Material sustainability matter	303	This code represents the sustainability matters (ESRS or entity-specific) identified by the undertaking as material in accordance with the DMA process.
Material sustainability matter	IRO	567	This code represents the impact, risk or opportunity related to material sustainability matters.

Source: Authors' work